

GROWTH RESPONSE OF WHITE YAM (*Descorea rotundata*) VARIETY TO DIFFERENT PLANTING TECHNIQUES FOR ENHANCING PRODUCTION

Odinwa A. B., Ukpong G., and Idibia F. A.

Article Info

Keywords: White Yam, Planting Techniques, Growth Response, Enhancing Production, Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.18890509

Abstract

This study was conducted in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku to determine the growth response of white yam to different planting techniques. The study adopted a complete randomized block design (CRBD) with three treatments, each replicates five (5) times and in five (5) experimental blocks. The treatments were three (3) planting methods- flat/mound, heap, and sack-bag techniques. Cultivation was performed during the first planting season of the year. Weeding, staking, and other cultural practices were duly observed. The sprouting rate, number of leaves, vine length, and number of vine branches were measured. The generated data were analyzed using percentage and mean separated using Duncan's multiple range scale. The findings showed that the parameters tested were numerically and significantly different among treatments at certain stages of growth, particularly at 5 WAP, but the numerical increase was not significantly different among treatments at 6 WAP. It was concluded that the three planting methods can effectively support yam growth and the choice of planting method should be determined by resource availability, land conditions and management objectives.

Introduction

Yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) is one of the essential tuber crops and a traditional food crop appreciated for its taste and cultural role in West Africa, especially in Nigeria, as the world's largest producer of yams, with annual production estimated at 45 million metric tons (UN Food & Agriculture Organization, 2017, Odinwa et al., 2019). Yam is regarded as a socio-cultural crop and is becoming expensive in urban areas as its production is no longer coping with population growth, leading to demand rising over and above supply (Kushwala & Polycarp, 2001).

A recent study on yam has shown that the absolute level of production in West Africa and the world has remained static for three decades (Odinwa et al., 2019). The static or dwindling trend may not be unconnected with production resources that are not being resourcefully used, leading to low crop productivity (Fasasi, 2006). The importance of yam as both a socio-economic and a socio-cultural crop cannot be overstated in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA) of Rivers State. The tuber can add value when processed into crude flour by drying thin slices in the sun, then pounding and grinding them into flour, thereby empowering those engaged in the processing. Yam enterprise can provide job opportunities to processors and marketers as a means of livelihood, given the necessary managerial attention required at each stage.

Yet, yam production is still under-exploited in the state where it is highly consumed as a staple and practiced as a foremost and kingly occupation by the farmers. From available proofs, yam farms in major parts of ONELGA are below subsistence levels as outputs are very low to meet the local demand for the products. Testing the growth rate of the different planting techniques (such as ridges or mounds/flat soil or sack bag) of planting white yam variety is essential for optimizing yield, reducing losses and encouraging mass participation to enhance yam production in the area.

Statement of the Problem

Yam production is expected to have reached a vintage level and be sustained in ONELGA, Rivers State in particular, especially now that the extension agencies operating in the area have unveiled its socio-economic and socio-cultural importance and international commodity status since the 1980s. However, this is not the case. Visible yam production has been running down the steep slope of extinction for over twenty-five years, yet its consumption has been uncontrollably increasing in the area (Odinwa et al., 2020).

Worst still, communities that were producing and celebrating annual New Yam Festivals with yams produced from their farms apriori are now buying yams from neighbouring States to celebrate their New Yam Festivals. Could it be that their production methods have failed or that their soils are no longer responding to yam growth? Therefore, the need for answers to these inspiring questions necessitated this study.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to examine the growth response of White Yam (*Descorea rotundata*) variety to different planting techniques for enhancing production.

The specific objectives were to examine the following:

- i. sprouting rate of the white yam variety following different planting techniques,
- ii. vine length of the white yam variety to different planting techniques from sprouting,
- iii. leaf count of the white yam variety to different planting techniques from sprouting, and
- iv. Number of vine branches of the white yam variety to different planting techniques a few weeks after sprouting.

Ho: Growth responses of the white-yam variety are not significantly affected by different planting techniques.

Materials and Methods

The research was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA), Rivers State. It was an experimental field study; the design adopted was CRBD with three treatments each replicated five (5) times and in five (5) experimental blocks. The treatments were three (3) planting methods; flat/hole, heap/mound and sack/bag. The experimental site was cleared, stumped and marked out. Seedbeds were constructed randomly on the plots according to predetermined parameters in each replicate at a planting distance of 1m by 1m, a foot path of 0.6m by 6m separating each replicate. Each experimental plot measured 33m by 6.6m, and the total

cultivation area was 33m by 29.2m. The seed yams were planted during the first planting season in March 2025, properly staked, and weeded regularly to keep the plots free from weeds throughout the experiment. The setup was properly monitored, and every other cultural practice in farm maintenance was observed.

Measurements were taken on sprouting, vine length, number of leaves and number of vine branching, which began from two weeks after planting (2WAP) to six (6 WAP).

Data generated were analyzed using percentages (descriptive statistics tool) for sprouting rate and the Duncan harmonic means for separation, which was used to analyze the other three growth variables.

Results and Discussion

a. Sprouting Rate of Yams in Bags, Heaps/Mounds, and Flats Two to Six Weeks after Planting

Table 1 shows that the sprouting pattern of yam varied across the three planting methods (bag, heap/mound, and flat/hole). At 2 weeks after planting (WAP), the flat method recorded the highest sprouting rate (67%), whereas the heap method had the lowest (30%). This indicates that yams planted on flat soils had a more favorable early establishment than those planted on heaps and bags. By 4WAP, all treatments had shown significant progress, with heap catching up (86.67%), bag recording 67%, and flat slightly higher at 70%. At 6WAP, all three tested variables reached comparable sprouting levels (83%–100%), indicating that the initial disparities in emergence diminished with time.

Table 1: Percentage distribution of the sprouting rates of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two – six weeks after planting

Variables/ Treatments	2WAP		3WAP		4WAP		5WAP		6WAP	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Bag	2.80 ^b	47.00	3.00 ^a	50.00	4.00 ^a	67.00	6.00 ^a	100.00	6.00 ^a	100.00
Heap/Mound	1.80 ^b	30.00	3.00 ^a	50.00	5.20 ^a	86.67	5.00 ^a	83.33	6.00 ^a	100.00
Flat/Hole	4.00 ^a	67.00	4.00 ^a	67.00	4.20 ^a	70.00	6.00 ^a	100.00	5.00 ^a	83.33

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different; WAP, weeks after planting

The findings indicate that the initial advantage of flat/hole planting in promoting early sprouting may be linked to better soil-seed contact and moisture retention, whereas heap and bag systems may have slower sprouting due to soil compaction or reduced water availability. However, because all treatments reached similar sprouting percentages by 6WAP, the planting method may not significantly affect the final sprouting success, but flat planting ensures more uniform early crop establishment.

b. Vine Length of yams planted in bags, heaps, and flat soils two–six weeks after planting

With vine elongation as a critical indicator of yam vigor and across the observation period in Table 2, flat planting consistently produced longer vines, with a mean length of 111.65 cm, compared to bag (99.53 cm) and heap (97.51 cm). By the fourth week, flat planting recorded a significant advantage (130.96 cm) over bag (94.28 cm) and heap (107.04 cm). However, at 5WAP, a stagnation was observed in the flat method (130.98 cm), possibly due to environmental stress or a temporary setback, but it rebounded strongly at 6WAP (164.90 cm), as shown in the results.

Table 2: Duncan's mean distribution on the vine length of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two–six weeks after planting

Variables	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	Total	Mean
Bag	55.34 ^a	65.55 ^a	94.28 ^a	126.67 ^a	155.78 ^a	497.62 ^a	99.53 ^a
Heap/Mound	29.96 ^a	55.59 ^a	107.04 ^a	132.68 ^a	162.24 ^a	487.51 ^a	97.51 ^a

Flat/hole	47.90 ^a	83.48 ^a	130.96 ^a	130.98 ^a	164.90 ^a	558.22 ^a	111.65 ^a
-----------	--------------------	--------------------	---------------------	---------------------	---------------------	---------------------	---------------------

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different; WAP- weeks after planting

This result implies that the superiority of flat planting in vine length reviewing that unrestricted root development and favourable soil moisture facilitated rapid vegetative growth. Although supportive, bags and heaps may restrict growth due to limited soil volume (bags) or excessive drainage (heaps). The temporary dip in vine growth at 5WAP under flat planting may indicate a short-term nutrient or water imbalance; however, the strong recovery highlights the resilience of the plant.

c. Number of leaves of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two–six weeks after planting

Table 3 indicates that leaf production followed a similar trend to vine length. At 2WAP, both mound/flat (5.20) and bag (5.40) had higher leaf numbers than heap (3.20), reviewing better initial establishment. By 4WAP, mound/flat planting showed a clear advantage with 12.29 leaves compared with 7.80 (bag) and 8.80 (heap). At 6WAP, mound/flat planting maintained the lead (13.47 leaves), with heap (13.40) and bag (12.20) following closely. The mean number of leaves was highest in the mound/flat (10.42), compared to the heap (8.52) and bag (8.36).

Table 3: Duncan's mean distribution on the number of leaves of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two–six weeks after planting

Variables	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	Total	Mean
Bag	5.40 ^a	7.20 ^a	7.80 ^a	9.20 ^a	12.20 ^a	41.80 ^a	8.36 ^a
Heap	3.20 ^a	6.00 ^a	8.80 ^a	11.20 ^a	13.40 ^a	42.60 ^a	8.52 ^a
Mound/Flat	5.20 ^a	8.66 ^a	12.29 ^a	12.46 ^a	13.47 ^a	52.08 ^a	10.42 ^a

Means with same superscript are not significantly different; WAP–weeks after plant

The results indicate that since leaves are the primary sites of photosynthesis, the higher leaf count in the flat method implies greater assimilate production, which is crucial for tuber bulking. The relatively lower leaf production in bag and heap systems may reflect the limitations in nutrient availability or soil volume. Nonetheless, the narrowing gap by 6WAP reviewing that all methods can eventually sustain adequate leaf production.

d. Number of vine branches of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two–six weeks after planting

Table 4 shows that branching started in all treatments from the third week, with progressive increases until 6WAP. The mean number of branches was highest in flat planting (1.96), followed by heap (1.88) and bag (1.80). By the sixth week, all methods produced comparable branch numbers (5.20–5.40).

Table 4: Duncan's mean distribution of the number of vine branches of yams planted in Bags, Heaps and Flat soils two–six weeks after planting

Variables	2WAP	3WAP	4WAP	5WAP	6WAP	Total	Mean
Bag	0.00 ^a	0.40 ^a	1.00 ^a	2.40 ^a	5.20 ^a	9.00 ^a	1.80 ^a
Heap	0.00 ^a	0.40 ^a	1.00 ^a	2.60 ^a	5.40 ^a	9.40 ^a	1.88 ^a
Mound/Flat	0.00 ^a	0.60 ^a	1.60 ^a	2.40 ^a	5.20 ^a	9.80 ^a	1.96 ^a

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different; WAP-weeks after planting

This finding indicates that vine branching was relatively uniform across treatments, with only slight superiority in flat/hole planting. Because branching influences canopy spread and photosynthetic efficiency, higher branching in flat planting reviewing better structural growth. However, the absence of statistically significant differences indicates that all three methods are equally supportive of branching at the early growth stages.

Agronomic implications of growth responses in yam production

The flat/hole technique consistently outperformed bag and heap in terms of vine length, leaf number, and branching, indicating its superiority for vigorous vegetative growth. Early sprouting was the fastest in the flat method, giving it an advantage in the establishment of uniform stands, which is critical for yam management. Bags and heaps, while slightly delayed in early growth, caught up in sprouting and leaf production by 6WAP, reviewing that they remain viable planting options under specific soil or environmental conditions. The statistical results (similar superscripts) showed that differences were not significant at the 5% level, meaning that flat planting demonstrated better numerical performance than the heap or bag method.

Conclusion

Flat/hole planting appears to provide a more favourable environment for yam growth within the first six weeks, particularly in terms of vine elongation and leaf production. However, because statistical tests indicate no significant differences among variables/treatments, all three methods can effectively support yam growth. However, the choice of planting method may depend on resource availability, land conditions, and management objectives.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study recommended all three methods of yam planting to farmers subject to resource availability, land conditions, and management objectives. However, where rapid and vigorous early growth is desired, the flat/hole method is recommended.

References

- Fasasi, A. R. (2006). Resource Use Efficiency in Yam Production in Ondo State, Nigeria Agricultural Journal, 1(2), 36-40.
- Kushwaha, S. & Polycap, I. M. (2001). Small-Scale Yam Production in Julian Pau LGA of the Plateau State Proceedings of 39th Annual Conference of ASN, ATBU, Bauchi, October 15-19. 69-74.
- Odinwa, A. B., Isife, B. I., & Nlerum, F. E. (2019). Analysis of the extension needs of yam increased productivity in Rivers and Imo States, Nigeria. International Journal of Agriculture, Environment and Bioresearch. 2004; 4(6):162–178.
- Odinwa, A. B., Emah, G. N., & Nlerum, F. E. (2020). Assessment of agricultural production Services delivered to yam farmers in Rivers and Imo States, Nigeria. International Journal of Innovative Agriculture and Biology Research, 8(2), 21-28.